

RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA

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Abstract: This article provides information on trade relations and relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the United States of America..

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Enter. There is a great opportunity for further development of trade relations between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the United States of America. The volume of mutual trade has recently increased by 61.2%, and this figure has exceeded 580 million dollars by the end of 2019. Our opinion is confirmed by the fact that US General Motors, Hyatt, Hilton, General Electric, John Deere, Boeing, Honeywell, Exxon Mobil, Coca-Cola and other companies are actively cooperating with Uzbekistan. The American-Uzbekistan Chamber of Commerce, established in 1993, plays an important role in effective communication between the business circles of the two countries. This organization regularly holds business forums and cooperative exchanges, serving to strengthen direct contact with potential partners.

In June 2019, for the first time, a trade representative office was established in Tashkent with the participation of 13 large American companies at the initiative of the US Minister of Commerce V. Ross.

Analyzes. Sovereign equality of states of Uzbekistan, non-use of force or threat of force, inviolability of borders, non-interference in internal affairs of other states; conscientious fulfillment of international obligations, respect and protection of human rights and other universally recognized principles and norms of international law; is interested in expanding cooperation with all partners in the path of peace, development and prosperity based on the basic principles of indivisibility of security, openness and pragmatism, development of good neighborly relations with neighboring countries in all aspects, strengthening of regional and international cooperation /.

One of the main and first-level tasks of foreign political activity is the effective implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks are assigned to the foreign policy office:

- formation of the most favorable external political conditions for the effective implementation of democratic reforms and the rapid processes of modernization of society and economy in our country;
- maintaining and strengthening peace and stability in Central Asia, turning the region into a region of security and sustainable development;
- formation of a balanced, multifaceted system of strategic cooperation with the world's leading countries and international organizations;
- Promotion of Uzbekistan's international initiatives in important areas of regional and world politics;
- assistance in increasing the volume of export of local products and expanding their geography;
- to provide active support in attracting foreign direct investments and advanced technologies to the priority sectors of the national economy;
- providing practical assistance in attracting tourists to our country and developing touristic infrastructure;
- to support the expansion and deepening of cooperation in the field of transport and transit and the development of international transport communications and logistics infrastructures;
- ensuring comprehensive protection of the rights and interests of citizens and legal entities of the Republic of Uzbekistan abroad;
- strengthening relations with compatriots living abroad.

The main priority of our foreign policy is the Central Asian region. Uzbekistan's policy in Central Asia is aimed at ensuring peace and stability in the region, solving important problems of regional security, including helping to solve the situation in Afghanistan. Uzbekistan will make every effort to strengthen regional trade and economic cooperation, develop the transport and transit infrastructure of the region, rational and comprehensive use of the water and energy resources of the transboundary rivers of Central Asia, ensure the ecological stability of the region, and complete the process of border delimitation and demarcation. - performs actions. Uzbekistan is interested in strengthening friendly and harmonious neighborly relations with the countries of the region, developing scientific-technical and cultural-humanitarian cooperation, strengthening relations between parliaments, border regions, public organizations and ordinary citizens. humanitarian cooperation is also developing at a steady pace. The main document regulating relations in this regard is the intergovernmental agreement on scientific

and technical cooperation adopted in 2010. Also, Tashkent and Seattle, Bukhara and Santa Fe are sister cities. In the field of education, a number of higher educational institutions in Uzbekistan have established relations with J. Hopkins University, higher educational institutions in the states of Washington, Indiana, California and Ohio.

Stanley Escudero, the second US ambassador to Uzbekistan, was the country's first chief diplomat in Tajikistan. According to Escudero, who witnessed the civil war and bloody events there, Karimov tried to make unprecedented changes in the first five years of independence. He established international relations, says the diplomat, but he gradually closed the economy of Uzbekistan, and this was a big mistake, says Escudero. He recalled that in the early 1990s, the republic was facing serious political and social challenges. The times when the society cannot yet feel what independence is, when the system has to start everything from scratch, it is clearly felt how difficult it is to achieve prosperity, no matter how hard the people work, and when they realize that stability is important first of all, the American legislator, the US Congress, in relation to Uzbekistan " He also assured that he is committed to passing the bill to end the application of the Jackson-Venik amendment. This is very important because it helps to establish a normal non-discriminatory trade relationship between the two countries.

During the visit, the Uzbek delegation handed over a collection of books from the project "Cultural heritage of Uzbekistan in world collections" to the Library of Congress. For a long time, the USA has expressed its strong support for Uzbekistan's WTO membership. In particular, this was emphasized during the meeting between Tanzila Norboyeva and US Deputy Trade Representative (USTR) Christopher Wilson in Washington on July 18.

According to Wilson, the United States is committed to supporting Uzbekistan's efforts to become a member of the WTO. In this regard, he expressed the readiness of the American side to participate in the 5th meeting of the working group on the accession of Uzbekistan to the WTO. Recognizing the complexity of this process, K.Wilson emphasized the continuous support of the American side in this matter," the official release said.

Conclusion. The deputy trade representative noted that USTR is interested in further expanding cooperation with Uzbekistan in support of common priorities within the Framework Agreement on Trade and Investment between Central Asian countries and the United States (TIFA).

At the meeting held at the US Ministry of Labor, the parties discussed the implementation of the \$2 million project "Increasing transparency and accountability in the cotton industry of Uzbekistan". In addition to political relations, relations with the USA have become more active in other directions.

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